

A Grounded Typology of Intertextual References in Malawian Digital Advertising

Author:

Mallick Mnela , *MCIM*

MSc Digital Marketing, Liverpool John Moores University

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Affiliations:

Liverpool John Moores University, Student

Chartered Institute of Marketing (UK), Elected Member

Digital Marketing Institute (DMI), Power Member

Email: mallickm3@gmail.com

Abstract

Intertextuality, a concept rooted in linguistics, shapes meaning in advertising but often remains abstract, particularly in African markets where Western frameworks, often rooted in literary theory, are misaligned with local communication practices and can appear forced. This study addresses this gap by providing a guiding typology of intertextual references for Malawian digital advertising. *Constructivist grounded theory* was applied to 500 Facebook and YouTube adverts (July 2020 - July 2025), and intercoder reliability was assessed on a 100-advert purposive sample reflecting observed proportions, with analysis including typology development. Three categories emerged - *Direct* (12.2%), *Indirect* (56.0%), and *Non-Referential* (31.8%) - comprising 21 subcategories distributed as 8 *Direct*, 10 *Indirect*, and 3 *Non-Referential*, offering detailed guidance for interpreting intertextual content. *Direct references* rely on culturally unmistakable layered meanings, *Indirect references* on implicit, culturally specific cues, and *Non-Referential* focus on core brand communication and serve as a baseline. Reliability was substantial, with Fleiss' $\kappa = 0.64$ (95% CI 0.61–0.73, $p < 0.001$), indicating strong agreement among coders and a narrow confidence interval that demonstrates the estimate is stable. The typology illustrates how digital advertising conveys local cultural meaning, providing a practical framework that bridges theory and practice and informs sub-Saharan African markets.

Keywords: *Intertextuality, Digital Advertising, Malawi, Grounded Theory, Typology, Advertising Strategy, Cultural Resonance*

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1. Introduction

Intertextuality - the practice of referencing other texts - has been widely studied across literary theory, linguistics, media studies, and cultural analysis. Early *structuralist models*, such as those by *Riffaterre (1987)* and *Genette (1982, 1997)*, focused on textual relationships through concepts like *obligatory, optional, and accidental references*, as well as *transtextual* and *paratextual structures*. *Kristeva (1980)* expanded this view by introducing *horizontal* and *vertical intertextuality*, while *Fairclough (1992)* offered a discourse-based lens, distinguishing *manifest intertextuality* from *interdiscursivity*. *Devitt (1991)* talks about *referential intertextuality* as the “reference in one text to other texts” (p. 342).

Over time, intertextuality scholarship has moved beyond *formalist approaches*. *Post-structural* and *postmodern theorists* - such as *Allen (2000)* have framed intertextuality as a broader cultural and communicative process. Newer perspectives have explored *multimodal intertextuality* (*Xing & Feng, 2023*), *persuasive metatextuality* in marketing (*Peterson, 2005*), and classifications based on visibility, such as *acknowledged* and *anonymous references* in advertising (*Conradie, 2012*). Scholars like *Ram (2016)* have proposed *communicative* and *referential typologies*, while others have combined literary theory with media analysis to develop *interdisciplinary frameworks* (*Lestari, 2022*).

In advertising research, dominant intertextual frameworks tend to focus on surface-level techniques such as pastiche, parody, and humour (*Hutcheon & O’Flynn, 2024*). These models foreground stylistic features but often overlook the strategic function of intertextuality in brand communication. Most are rooted in Western literary theoretical traditions (*Kristeva, 1980; Genette, 1997; Allen, 2000*) and are commonly applied to African contexts without adequate consideration of local media ecologies, cultural logics, or audience reception (*Conradie, 2012; Xing & Feng, 2023*).

This study offers a different approach. While literary intertextuality focuses on formal and structural relationships between texts, the taxonomy proposed here is grounded in the functional role of intertextuality in advertising - how it drives brand positioning, supports campaign goals, and navigates competitive dynamics. The emphasis shifts from form to function, aligning intertextual strategies with marketing objectives. Developed through grounded theory and based on analysis of 500 digital adverts in Malawi, the framework reflects how intertextuality operates in local practice to construct meaning, engage audiences, and respond to commercial imperatives.

Intertextuality is now pervasive in digital advertising globally (*Hackley & Hackley, 2022; Xing & Feng, 2023*). Brands use it to leverage shared cultural references and foster recognition. In Malawi, however, its use is often unstructured, lacking strategic clarity and theoretical grounding. Much of the existing research is Western and conceptually driven, often disconnected from the realities of African advertising markets. These studies tend to assume competitive, individualistic economies and rarely account for local infrastructure, media consumption habits, or cultural priorities (*Enesiti, 2010; Nwaefuna, 2022*).

This study addresses that gap. Using grounded theory (*Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Strauss & Corbin, 1990; Charmaz, 2014*), it analyses digital adverts to develop a practical typology of intertextual references. Rather than rely on abstract categories such as *allusion* or *pastiche* (*Genette, 1997; Allen, 2000*), the proposed framework identifies three main intertextual/non-intertextual classes, each with detailed subcategories as illustrated in **Table 1** below:

Table 1: *Established Practical Intertextual Typology for Malawian Digital Adverts*

Type	Subcategories
Direct Intertextuality	<i>Confrontational, by-stander, parodic, retaliatory, emotional, collaborative, user-generated content (UGC) and cross-media.</i>
Indirect Intertextuality	<i>Suspended/delayed, cultural, historic, temporal, eWOM spillover, gamified, subtle parodic, narrative, comparative, and implicit UGC.</i>
Non-Referential	<i>Brand communication, product communication, and crisis communication.</i>

Non-Referential Adverts, which make up 31.8% of the dataset, are often left out in traditional intertextuality studies. Their inclusion in this typology shows that the lack of references is not a weakness but a deliberate strategy. In Malawi's context, advertisers often prioritise clarity, trust, and direct messaging over complex or layered references. Research shows that low-complexity adverts tend to perform better in high-context or low-literacy settings (Lagerwerf & Meijers, 2008; Huhmann, Mothersbaugh & Franke, 2002).

The typology also captures symbolic, visual, and digital-native strategies within Malawi's online advertising. It aligns with De Mooij's (2019) view that culture strongly influences message design, especially where directness is preferred.

This study offers a context-aware, practice-driven framework that helps advertisers, researchers, and regulators in understanding how meaning is constructed, interpreted, and operationalised in Malawian digital campaigns using intertextuality.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data Collection and Coding

This study employed a constructivist grounded theory approach (Charmaz, 2014; Strauss & Corbin, 1990; Glaser & Strauss, 1967) to analyse 500 digital advertisements produced in Malawi between 2020 and 2025. The dataset was drawn from *Facebook* and *YouTube*, the country's dominant platforms for digital brand communication.

A *purposive stratified sampling strategy* was adopted to ensure sectoral and thematic diversity. Adverts were stratified by sector based on ten sectors: *telecommunications, banking, FMCG, retail, health care, education, insurance, hospitality, parastatals/government, and NGOs*. Selection criteria included reach, frequency of reposts or shares, and the presence of intertextual or symbolic elements. Each advert was treated as a discrete unit of analysis. Coding followed the three-stage grounded theory process: open coding to identify initial themes, axial coding to establish conceptual links, and selective coding to refine core categories. Adverts were grouped into three primary categories: *Direct Reference, Indirect Reference, and No Reference (Non-Referential)*. Subcategories emerged through constant comparison, guided by communicative intent, strategic function, visual and linguistic design, and cultural context. Coders also identified informally circulating content relevant to brand narratives.

Data extraction combined digital and manual methods. *Facepager* was used to retrieve *Facebook* data, while *YouTube* content was gathered manually through direct observation and transcription. Google Sheets served as the collaborative platform for coding, memo writing, and frequency tracking. Coding was performed manually by 20 trained marketers, each

advert coded independently by at least two coders. Discrepancies were resolved through consensus in peer-review sessions. *Average intercoder* agreement was 78 %, demonstrating consistent and rigorous application of the coding scheme. Data saturation was reached at 360 adverts, after which no new categories emerged. Remaining adverts were coded to confirm robustness. The final typology includes *21 subcategories nested within the three main reference types*.

2.2 Typology Validation and Intercoder Reliability

The reliability and validity of the three-category coding scheme - *Direct, Indirect, and Non-referential* - were assessed in a two-stage process. For a comprehensive breakdown of intercoder reliability statistics, please refer to *Appendix 2*.

2.2.1 Intercoder Reliability

Twenty trained coders, independent of the original labelling, classified 100 purposively selected adverts (*12 Direct, 56 Indirect, 32 Non-referential*), with each advert coded by all coders. Overall observed agreement was 77.95 %, and *Fleiss' κ* was 0.66 (95 % CI [0.61, 0.73], $p < 0.001$), indicating substantial agreement (*Landis & Koch, 1977*). Category-level agreement against reference labels is summarised in *Table 2*. Lower agreement for *Direct references* reflects the small sample size, where few disagreements disproportionately affect results.

Table 2: *Category-Level Agreement*

Category	Sample (n)	Observed Agreement
<i>Non-referential</i>	32	88 %
<i>Indirect</i>	56	79 %
<i>Direct</i>	12	73 %
Overall	100	78 %

2.2.2 Typology Validation

A two-round *Delphi* process with 20 experts (*academics and practitioners with ≥ 5 years' experience in Malawian digital marketing*) assessed the typology's clarity, distinctiveness, relevance, and completeness. Feedback from round one informed revisions, and round two confirmed consensus (≥ 80 % agreement). This process ensured the typology is both theoretically robust and practically relevant, reinforcing reliability and validity (*Spiggle, 1994; Belk, 2006; Tracy, 2010; Sinkovics & Alfoldi, 2012*). Combined, intercoder analysis and expert review demonstrate that the coding scheme and typology are reliable, valid, and grounded in Malawian digital advertising practice.

3. Results

i. Key Findings

a. Intertextual Categories Identified

This study offers a grounded typology linking intertextuality to strategic advertising practice. Unlike traditional approaches that emphasise style, this work focuses on intertextuality's role in shaping brand meaning and audience engagement. Based on the analysis of actual Malawian digital adverts, it shows how local campaigns use intertextual references to meet marketing goals. The typology moves from form to function, aligning creative choices with strategic intent. Three main categories emerged: *direct*, *indirect*, and *non-referential*, further divided into 21 subtypes (8 direct, 10 indirect, 3 non-referential). This classification captures how brands position themselves and communicate meaning online. For creatives, it offers a tool to select intertextual strategies that fit local styles. For strategists, it enables more deliberate brand positioning rooted in real practice.

b. Reference Fatigue in Popular Segments

High levels of repetition were observed in certain market segments, leading to *reference fatigue* - a pattern where the overuse of familiar references reduces engagement and impact. This concept draws from the notion of *advert fatigue* or *advert overload* in digital marketing (Tayeb et al., 2025; Silberstein, Shoham & Klein, 2023; Hitchon and Jura, 1997).

c. Preference for Subtle or Non-Referential Strategies

Brands often avoided overt intertextuality. Subtle or non-referential content was more common than direct references, pointing to a cautious, context-aware approach. In Malawi, non-reference adverts were particularly frequent - *Retail* (60%), *Parastatals* (52%), and *Hospitality* (34%). Including these adverts provides necessary contrast, showing where intertextuality is consciously avoided - or possibly overlooked.

In some cases, the absence of references may reflect limited awareness of intertextual strategy, lack of creative capacity, or focus on compliance and clarity. Prior studies show that in regulated sectors such as health, finance, or government, advertisers often favour straightforward messaging over stylistic complexity (McQuarrie & Mick, 1999; De Mooij, 2019). In high-risk or low-context environments, messages tend to be stripped of metaphor or symbolism to avoid misinterpretation (Hall, 1976; Luna & Peracchio, 2001). In emerging markets, trust and transparency may take precedence over narrative depth (Okazaki & Mueller, 2007; Nwaefuna, 2022). These patterns challenge the idea that intertextuality is always a desirable or expected feature of advertising. Accounting for non-referential adverts expands the scope of analysis - not just in terms of what is said, but also what is unsaid and why. In such settings, absence can be as meaningful as presence.

The dominance of indirect or subtle intertextual references reflects the need to reduce reputational risk, allow interpretive flexibility, maintain cultural relevance, and support strategic brand positioning (Mueller, 2011; Okazaki & Mueller, 2007; Keller, 2020). Several situations favour this approach:

Table 3: *Justifying Inclusion of Non-Referential Adverts*

Category	Description	Goal	Advantage
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Institutional Messaging	NGOs, public institutions, and parastatals use clear, policy-driven communication.	Awareness, not persuasion	Clear communication of policies.
Trust and Compliance	In regulated sectors or where neutrality matters, layered messaging is avoided.	Maintain trust and ensure compliance	Safer, more trusted approach.
Routine Updates	Direct, no-frills messaging is used for essential product or service announcements.	Provide essential information	Effective for product/service announcements.

While these adverts are unlikely to offend and are easy to understand, they may lack the emotional pull or memorability of intertextual approaches. Still, their frequency shows their relevance in daily communication.

ii. Typology Overview

This typology identifies three main categories of intertextuality in Malawian digital advertising:

Direct Intertextuality

Adverts that use *direct or layered cues* - such as figures of speech, mimicry, or recognisable symbols - to lead to an *unmistakable reference* to a known text, brand, or public figure. While individual elements may seem subtle, their accumulation results in clear, unmistakable recognition. This approach supports collaboration, confrontation, or appropriation of buzz. It is the least common at 12.2%, showing that even direct references often rely on culturally embedded subtlety and more layered references.

Indirect Intertextuality

Adverts that imply or allude to external content through cultural cues, trends, or shared history. Most common (56.0%), showing reliance on context-driven, high-context messaging.

Non-Referential Adverts

Adverts with no external references. Focused on the brand's own message. *Non-referential adverts*, though they may seem separate from intertextuality, are better seen as part of it. *Kristeva (1980)* and *Barthes (1977)* argue that all texts draw meaning from other texts, even when not obvious. This means that adverts without clear references still rely on shared ways of speaking or thinking. *Genette (1997)* and *Fairclough (1992)*, however, show that intertextuality can be strong or weak. Some texts, like these adverts, use few or no external references on purpose. In Malawian advertising, their high share (31.8%) suggests a clear strategy - avoiding outside links to keep messages simple, direct, and less open to misinterpretation, especially in formal or sensitive settings.

Emerging Categories in the study can be described follows:

A. Direct Intertextual Categories

1. Confrontational Intertextual References

As outlined by *Bazerman (2004, p. 87)*, some adverts used *confrontational intertextuality* to position brands within competitive tensions. In this study, such adverts employed visual rhetoric, parody, and wordplay to mock rival brands directly. These resemble hijacked adverts, where professional mimicry and disparaging content are used to challenge or undermine competing brands (*Thota & Villarreal, 2020*).

This was most evident in the telecommunications and banking sectors, where brand rivalry is more pronounced. *Chang and Kinnucan (1991)* highlight that in saturated markets, combative advertising has the potential to shift consumer preferences, but it does not necessarily increase overall demand. In telecommunications, TNM's June 2025 campaign responded to Airtel's 'Mo Faya' data bundles campaign by parodying its central metaphor. TNM used firefighting visuals - extinguishers, emergency scenes, and a burnt character - to undermine the 'fire' theme. The *wordplay* was clear and deliberate. While Airtel promoted "Mo Faya," TNM countered with: "Don't let the Faya burn your pockets." This *confrontational intertextuality* served both as satire and strategic critique, reinforcing TNM's positioning as the more affordable alternative.

Image 1: TNM adverts making confrontational reference to Airtel's 'Mo Faya' campaign. Source: Telekom Networks Malawi, 2025. Available at:

<https://www.facebook.com/Telekomnetworksmalawi/posts/pfbid0T55MjP5fMXWtMLJGF6UgtrdYiLMbw3r4ou7jXsdLZ68idzLnRRjKLXLdFXspaeuxl> [Accessed 27 July, 2025].

In banking, similar strategies were observed, with adverts using *confrontational intertextuality* to target rival brands. National Bank released an advert centred on the phrase "Greatness starts with setting Standard," clearly positioned as a critique of Standard Bank. The advert employed *visual metaphor* by styling the word "Standard" in Standard Bank's corporate colours - subtly undermining the competitor while asserting its own claims to leadership. The use of the visual cues in this context points to a deliberate communicative

tactic aimed at influencing consumer perception through *ridicule* and *contrast*, thus building some competitive tension.

2. Retaliatory Intertextual Reference

Retaliatory intertextuality occurs when a brand responds to a provocative or competitive advert with direct parody or strategic imitation. These responses serve both as brand engagement and competitive positioning tactics (Vanden Bergh et al., 2015; Xing & Feng, 2023). In Malawi, such instances often follow *confrontational intertextuality*. A notable example followed National Bank's 2021 "setting standards" campaign. In response, Standard Bank released an advert highlighting its "24/7" service - a reference to its *247# USSD code. The phrase "6 to 6" was used to imply limited availability, widely interpreted as a jab at National Bank's *626# code. Though indirect, the comparison was deliberate and retaliatory.

In a separate case, FDH Bank launched a Whatsapp Banking campaign parodying rivals as outdated. The advert specifically mocked First Capital Bank (FCB) as a laggard. FCB responded with a satirical advert portraying a WhatsApp group made up of "friends of FHD" (a deliberate reversal of acronyms). The caption read: "We tried to click it once, but it never clicked" - a clear retort cloaked in humour.

Image 2: Retaliatory advert by First Capital Bank (FCB), referencing the earlier exchange between National Bank and Standard Bank, as outlined in the Confrontational Intertextuality section. (Source: FCB Malawi Facebook Page, 20 October 2021). Link: <https://www.facebook.com/FirstCapitalBankMalawi/posts/pfbid02XM6DBBYaOr3tZPSntsUZrys5xsSG6JL9u67kPu9hJLDr5Y3ot8DzhcfnvXbM21Ql> (Accessed 23 July, 2025)

3. By-Stander Intertextual Reference

We define *by-stander intertextuality* as a strategic reference type in which a brand exploits the symbolic capital of unrelated campaigns through parasitic association. Rather than investing in original storytelling, the brand benefits from the pre-existing audience awareness surrounding another campaign. As Heath and Heath (2007) explain, ideas that are already

“*cognitively sticky*” and “*salient*” reduce the mental effort required for engagement, making such borrowed associations more efficient for recall and relevance. *Fiske (1987)* refers to this kind of referential layering as part of an ‘*intertextual relay*’, where meaning is distributed across texts and reinforced by the audience’s recognition of familiar elements (Ott and Walter, 2000).

Image 3: A Bystander advert by Banja La Mtsogolo referencing the National Bank and Standard Bank banter, as discussed in the *Confrontational Intertextuality* section (Source: Banja La Mtsogolo Facebook Page, 20 Oct 2021).

Link: <https://www.facebook.com/blmmalawi/posts/pfbid0pLAdYU9sjcP4HwEFQCwdqGE7EfkYhVvE9n3xLEfpUB9JtVUTqd2GAF7rSxGPJqxyI> (Accessed 23 July, 2025)

4. Parodic Intertextuality

Parody in advertising functions both as a persuasive tool and cultural critique. *Hutcheon (1989)*, cited in *Federici (1996)*, describes parody as a practice that problematises value by critically engaging with earlier texts while recognising their historical and ideological context. In digital advertising, parody often mimics familiar formats, slogans, or competitor content to expose contradictions, challenge norms, or signal insider knowledge. This is especially relevant in Malawi, where cultural closeness allows audiences to quickly understand and appreciate the subversive or humorous intent. Thus, *parodic intertextuality* acts as both a rhetorical strategy and a form of ideological positioning.

Parody can effectively engage and humor audiences but requires careful execution to avoid legal issues. *Weinberger and Gulas (1992)* suggest parody in advertising succeeds with a balance of recognisability and exaggeration.

Image 4. FDH Bank advert employing parodic intertextuality to mock competitor banks. Source: FDH Bank, 2023. Available at:

<https://www.facebook.com/FDHMalawi/posts/pfbid024ikWNVUgBJMF2czGTm1EkEAYbPSTd69i2STUhJY4pJ16NQa5b51grg3UEXrZrFb3l> [Accessed 3 Aug. 2025].

An example from our corpus is FDH Bank's advert, which used parody by depicting a WhatsApp group called "WhatsApp Banking," humorously including FCB and NBS as members. The advert employed paratextual elements, positioning FDH Bank as the group leader while portraying FCB (*spelled FBC in the advert*) and NBS (*labelled NSB*) as lagging behind. For instance, FCB's brand assets - such as font and colour - were mockingly referenced, while NBS's well-known tag 'Eazy' was used. This parody engaged audiences with humour and satire, reinforcing FDH Bank's market leadership.

5. Collaborative Intertextual references

Collaborative intertextuality involves intentional partnerships between brands or between a brand and public figures to boost credibility, symbolic appeal, and reach. *Park, Jun and Shocker (1996)* show that composite branding strengthens perceived value when brand associations are strong and meaningful. *Helmig, Huber and Leeftang (2008)* argue that co-branding works best when brand fit and message clarity are maintained.

Airtel Malawi and TNM engaged in a collaborative reference with a *Valentine's Day* advert in 2024. Airtel invited TNM to a late lunch Valentine's date via a digital advert on Facebook. TNM responded with a similar post, tagging Airtel and using the same color scheme.

Image 5. Collaborative intertextual references between [Airtel Malawi](#) and TNM on Facebook during February 2024. Sources: Airtel Malawi and Telekom Networks Malawi, 2024. Available at: Airtel Malawi Facebook Page and Telekom Networks Malawi Facebook Page [Accessed 14 Feb. 2024].

Both brands used red and green to project their identities, creating a playful and cooperative interaction. This collaborative reference not only generated positive engagement from their audiences but also fostered a sense of camaraderie between the competing brands, enhancing their collective brand perception.

6. Cross-Media Intertextual References

Deng et al. (2020) describe genre hybridisation as the mixing of advertising with editorial or journalistic styles, referring to it as the invasion of the promotional genre. They explore this using both intertextual and interdiscursive lenses. *Fairclough (1992, 2003)* terms this overlap *constitutive intertextuality* - where one mode of communication borrows structure and authority from another.

In what this study calls cross-media intertextuality, adverts adopt the tone, language, or format of media content. Some reference news reports; others respond to circulating adverts or commentary. These messages tap into wider public discourse, using familiar media forms to build trust and credibility.

In 2021, for instance, FCB Bank referenced Edith Gondwe's viral article 'Do Me a Favour', published in *The Nation*, which commented on the culture of financial requests on social media. The bank's advert mirrored this theme through a WhatsApp-style image showing people asking for money, with the headline: "Do Them a Favor Through Our Digital Platforms." Linking its message to a trending media topic, FCB Bank most likely increased engagement and cultural relevance.

These references often involve advertising content drawn from viral interviews, television clips, or internet memes. One notable example is the phrase "Gagagaga," which gained significant public recognition following its use by an elderly woman in a televised interview

on Times TV with Brian Banda, where she delivered a sexually suggestive comment in a cryptic yet humorous manner. Another instance pertains to the widely publicised controversy regarding a purported fake PhD, involving prominent social media influencers, which was subsequently referenced in multiple digital advertisements. Such viral cultural moments were strategically repurposed to cultivate resonance and relatability among target audiences.

Used well, such references help brands connect with cultural trends. Used carelessly, they can trivialise serious issues or alienate audiences - what terms intertextual backlash, and *Dore (2020)* calls the boomerang effect. *Fairclough (1992)* also cautions that borrowing from other texts always involves ideological risks, especially when sensitive cultural content is co-opted. Media influence works both ways. From a regulatory point of view, targeting individuals in a way that violates their rights in adverts is discouraged (*Kachinjika, 2021*).

Just as adverts can draw from news content, news articles can also reflect on adverts, extending their reach and reframing their message. This movement across media forms introduces new layers of meaning and changes how the original communication is received. Cross-media referencing increasingly employs *QR codes (Ryu & Murdock, 2013)*, enabling advertisers to integrate direct links to external content - like video clips, WhatsApp prompts, or sign-up forms - within their adverts.

Image 6(a). News article reporting that TNM's advert mocked Airtel. Source: Malawi24, 2018. Available at: <https://malawi24.com/2018/01/22/tnm-mocks-airtel-advert> [Accessed 3 Aug. 2025].

Can you do me a favour?

My dear ladies, let's talk. This phrase: "Can you do me a favour?" is scaring men. Many of us are using it to beg. We are begging men for money, lifts, lunches, make-up and hair products. The list is endless and men are exhausted. We need to change.

It is obvious that naturally, we expect men to do certain things for us. These range from helping and spoiling us from time to time. But it is getting out of control. Men are opening up and admitting to exhaustion. Beautiful women who portray on social media as bosses are going into men's inboxes asking for almost everything—from airtime to their children's school fees.

This is degrading and harassment. We are harassing these men with our constant begging. Let men share what they have out of the goodness of their hearts and not because we are constantly begging and making them feel bad if they do not give us money.

A woman runs a home, but once she gets a boyfriend, all her needs are dumped on the man. Are we surprised why these men evade settling down? I think some expect too much too soon from a lover. He is your boyfriend not your donor.

You cannot get a boyfriend and ask him for a child's school fees a week later. That's a deal breaker. Once you make it a habit to rely on men, you become vulnerable. How do you stand your ground against abuse when the perpetrator is funding that posh lifestyle? That is why some women are tolerating emotional and physical abuse.

Through social media, some women have no shame asking for favours from random men. Once a man shows interest, the next text is asking for transport money, airtime, saloon etc. Where is our pride as ladies? I know some of us are struggling. But that does not give us a free pass with a begging bowl to any man. And yes, at some point we meet someone to support us. But this does not mean we should develop a lazy attitude or a lifestyle we cannot afford.

These men ain't as desperate as we think. After sometime, they get tired and once they do, they meet someone who has her own money. They will leave you for a woman they can also rely on in case of trouble. They are human too and want to be pampered, not always giving, giving and giving. So, dear ladies, can you do me a favour? Stop begging for money from men! ■

CANDID TALK

WITH EDITH GONDWE

Feedback WhatsApp: +265888346425

Do them a favor through our digital platforms.

F1RST MOBILE (DIAL *1111#)

Belief comes first.

Image 6(b): Original 'Do me a favour article' and FCB Advert (Sources: [Edith Gondwe/Nation Online](#) and FCB Facebook Page)

7. Emotional Intertextual Reference

Emotional intertextuality occurs when adverts draw on familiar texts, sounds, or stories to evoke emotions such as nostalgia, pride, joy, or humour. These emotional triggers strengthen audience connection and enhance message recall. Such references activate shared cultural memory, increasing emotional resonance. As argued by *Nemčoková (2014)*, stylistic blending in adverts can produce layered emotional effects that shape consumer attitudes. This approach aims to forge a personal link between the viewer and the brand.

Image 7. Emotional intertextuality advert evoking nostalgia. Source: Telekom Networks Malawi, 2023. Available at:

<https://www.facebook.com/Telekomnetworksmalawi/posts/pfbid0wpVgxUjZrxHrUTu2EHfcpK V61uvkVLC5WbWzeVjx6Ts1YjQzrWbyKAmzL8akVPHxl> [Accessed 3 Aug. 2025].

In 2021, for example, TNM released an advert for the low-cost *Tiago* phone that tapped into nostalgia. Targeting an older audience, it evoked memories of a time when owning a simple, popular device carried social value. Through the line “*Aka kanali ka nthawi iti?*” (*From which generation is this device?*), the advert reconnected audiences with earlier experiences, associating the brand with familiarity and simpler times.

8. User Generated Content (UGC)

User-generated intertextuality occurs when audiences remix, recreate, or circulate content that references existing adverts or brands, introducing new layers of meaning. Recent studies show this shifts narrative control from brands to users, who shape brand perception through memes and social media, raising questions around authenticity and trust (*Marwick & Lewis, 2023*). This is especially influential in digital markets, where peer-generated content spreads quickly and resonates across cultural contexts.

A strong example is linked to the brand banter between National Bank and Standard Bank, discussed under *confrontational* and *retaliatory intertextuality* above. In this case, an unidentified internet user produced and shared an advert appearing to represent FDH Bank. It featured the caption: ‘*Asiyeni omenyanawo. Ife ndi amtendere ndi ufulu*’ (*Leave them*

brawling. We are tolerant and peaceful), accompanied by caricatures fighting and the phrase 'Ufulu ndi 525' (Peace with 525).

Image 8(a). User-generated content purporting to represent FDH Bank, circulated via WhatsApp in 2023. Source: Unofficial UGC, 2021. Accessed via WhatsApp [20 Oct. 2021].

Although this user generated advert did not align with FDH Bank's official branding, it contributed to the wider conversation and attracted public attention online. It demonstrates how users engage with brand narratives, injecting humour and commentary that may travel further than official campaigns. The bank released the above *user-generated content (UGC)* advert labelled 'FAKE', distancing itself from the material while still benefitting from the surrounding buzz. This responding advert fits within a distinct category: *by-stander intertextuality* (See: p. 6).

Image 8(b). Bystander intertextuality triggered by FDH Bank's refutation of a user-generated advert falsely attributed to the brand. Source: FDH Bank, 2021. Available at: <https://www.facebook.com/FDHMalawi/posts/pfbid029dnjVTLTDkLLpJ4rNufnmcYbsqr3prYkH1BWE REUz9HOADjWwtqMcLZxSIONjjuEl> [Accessed 2 Aug. 2025].

There are several ways UGC plays a crucial role in advertising by blending consumer voices with brand narratives. Testimonials serve as trusted endorsements that significantly influence purchase decisions (Demba *et al.*, 2019). Memes, as a form of viral content, effectively engage younger audiences by tapping into online culture and humour, driving brand awareness and interaction (Dhir *et al.*, 2023; Yang, 2022). Hashtag campaigns and contests motivate users to create and share branded content, fostering participation and expanding reach (Demba *et al.*, 2019). Organic UGC, such as peer recommendations, spreads through social networks, enhancing credibility and trust (Leskovec, Adamic & Huberman, 2005). Unprompted mentions and reviews reflect genuine conversations and consumer feedback, which further shape brand perception and consumer attitudes (Čábyová, Darazs & Hudáková, 2024). Community discussions also contribute by allowing deeper user engagement and exchange of experiences. Together, these diverse forms of UGC build authenticity, increase relatability, and amplify advertising impact.

B. Indirect Intertextual References

1. Suspended Intertextual Referencing

Suspended intertextuality uses incomplete or ambiguous references to create suspense and invite interpretation. This approach engages audiences by triggering curiosity and sustaining attention. Eco's (1989) 'open work' and Barthes' (1977) 'readerly/writerly texts' illustrate how open-endedness encourages participation. Research links suspense and mystery to increased engagement and recall through cognitive and emotional investment (Yang & Smith, 2009).

Image 9. FDH Bank advert using delayed or suspended intertextual referencing. Source: FDH Bank, 2023. Available at:

<https://www.facebook.com/FDHMalawi/posts/pfbid0zL5AEdo9NvDUek2CkDSiVPtLFRP7KWcJED9TxgQqypwwudArPWQuyJwFod8QEpEdl> [Accessed 3 Aug. 2025].

In digital advertising, *suspended intertextual references* often unfold in stages, encouraging audiences to seek follow-up content and sparking viral discussion. Trehan (2012) discusses

how teaser campaigns serve as effective advertising tools across different sectors. This technique works well when audience interaction is key to campaign success. It is mostly used in telecommunications and banking.

In 2025, National Bank ran a *suspended intertextuality campaign* featuring a *mystery briefcase*, unveiled during a major female football sponsorship event. Instead of delivering information upfront, the campaign revealed content gradually, inviting the audience to piece together the message. This approach made the final reveal more impactful. *Suspended references* are especially effective in product launches or campaigns that rely on building anticipation.

2. Electronic Word of Mouth (eWoM) Intertextual Referencing

eWoM Spillover Intertextuality describes how brand messages cross borders and gain new meaning through electronic word-of-mouth. *Straubhaar (1991)* argues that ‘*cultural proximity*’ makes audiences more receptive to content from other regions when shared cultural cues exist. *Jenkins et al. (2013)* highlight audience agency - users actively reinterpret and circulate media, creating fresh meanings. *Lobato (2019)* notes this often happens through informal digital networks, outside official brand channels.

A typical example involves an [Airtel Kenya advert](#) featuring red and green colours and critiquing heavy data and talk-time consumption by a rival network. In Malawi, TNM’s brand colour is green, making the advert resonate strongly. It was widely shared informally, inadvertently giving Airtel Malawi some leverage.

Image 10(a). *Screengrabs from an example of eWOM spillover advert originally circulated by Airtel Kenya. Source: Airtel Kenya, 2022. Available at: <https://youtu.be/9fHVtuFZDQk> [Accessed 3 Aug. 2025].*

With cross-border memes, *eWOM spillover* occurs when adverts or viral content from neighbouring countries are reposted and recontextualised by local brands, offering audiences material they are already exposed to and find culturally relevant. In 2025, the *meerkat meme* spread through Nigeria, Kenya, and South Africa. When Malawian brands joined the trend, it resonated with digitally active audiences familiar with the meme. Those who engage regularly online are more likely to recognise the intertextual narrative in such content.

Image 10(b). BLM repurposing a viral meerkat meme in a follow-up eWOM spillover advert (Source: BLM Facebook Page, accessed 2 August 2025).

Link:

<https://www.facebook.com/blmmalawi/posts/pfbid0zUbE6SfZnrcgYqnUc2u5K3c1Xzb6NtdcqVF8ZM9Nq3SCZoiRGKVjF7ab6HjdEz9F1>

3. Gamified Intertextual References

Gamified intertextuality occurs when brands embed advertising within game environments, either through in-game placements or purpose-built branded games. These formats mix play with promotion, creating immersive experiences. *Van Berlo et al. (2022)* distinguish between in-game advertising - brands appearing in existing games - and advergaming, designed specifically around brand messages. While these approaches boost emotional engagement, users often focus more on gameplay than the brand message. Recent studies show gamified adverts can increase emotional response and interaction among audiences (*Hamari & Keronen, 2021; Elwakeel et al., 2025*). However, they caution that brand recall may decline when entertainment overshadows message clarity, highlighting the need for strategic integration of intertextual cues.

Image 11(a). FDH Bank's 'Spot the Ball' advert showcasing gamified intertextuality. Source: FDH Bank, 2023. Available at: <https://www.facebook.com/FDHMalawi/posts/pfbid0HbkNnj8BpTHqHbND7CF8zJHmVgTXmSs9wGPTbQzCANeskU98LQNHVfDwFiZP76Tfl> [Accessed 3 Aug. 2025].

In 2022, FDH Bank used a "Spot the Ball" quiz on its Facebook page. The focus was more on play than on brand engagement. Other brands can engage audiences through crossword puzzles, trivia, or other light-touch interactive formats that encourage participation without overt brand messaging.

Image 11(b): Airtel Malawi, 2022. Spin and Win advert showcasing gamified intertextuality [Facebook post], 18 December. Available at: <https://www.facebook.com/airtelmw/posts/pfbid03292H5OqVx6m3A9U2FAdzvUUh6pCeQBYddCwvFhumUXovCgLLv4JYdML7daiEQAWUI> [Accessed 3 August 2025].

In late 2024, Airtel Malawi introduced brand-aligned games within its mobile app, offering talk time and data as prizes. This incentive-driven approach attracted more users, encouraging them to download the My Airtel App to access Airtel services.

4. Cultural Intertextual References

Cultural intertextuality in advertising uses local customs, symbols, and references to build relevance and emotional connection. Research shows culturally adapted adverts outperform standardised ones, especially when authentic and context-specific (Hornikx et al., 2023). In high-context cultures, implicit cues work best (De Mooij, 2019). Banet-Weiser (2012) warns that misuse can provoke resistance and harm brand authenticity. For example, TNM's 2024 Africa Day advert, featuring the CEO in traditional Ngoni regalia, faced backlash and was withdrawn.

Airtel's use of "*faya*" instead of "*fire*" draws on Chichewa phonology and Pan-African popular culture, blending local speech with Afro-Caribbean music vernaculars. The call to action, "*Get Faya'd Up!*", informal language linked to Airtel's "*MoFaya PaNet Bundle*" to convey youthful energy. This slang targets younger audiences, reflecting the conversational style of youth culture and platforms like *TikTok*, making the advert more relatable and memorable compared to formal business language (Gretry et al., 2017; Goddard, 1998; Beukeboom, Kerkhof & de Vries, 2015).

Image 12. Airtel Malawi Cultural Intertextual References in Mo Faya Adverts: [Left](#) and [Right](#).
(Source: Airtel Malawi Facebook Page)

5. Historic Intertextual References

Historic intertextuality in advertising draws on shared cultural memory to evoke emotion and strengthen brand credibility. It involves referencing past events, national milestones, or iconic figures to trigger collective or personal nostalgia. These cues act as strategic memory anchors, linking brands to familiar histories and identities.

Assmann (2011) defines such references as part of "*cultural memory*" – social frameworks of remembrance passed through generations. Hutcheon (1988) sees this as '*postmodern recontextualisation*', where history is reframed to serve present needs.

In our study, 5.6% of adverts employed this approach, often tied to national pride, independence, or past social struggles. Examples include adverts referencing *Chilembwe Day*, *Kamuzu Day*, and *Independence Day* – moments that connect brands to culturally significant timelines.

Empirical research supports the effectiveness of this strategy. *Grappi et al. (2024)* found that nostalgic and historical cues increase emotional connection and brand love, particularly in markets with strong shared memories. A 2024 report by the African Marketing Confederation, based on research from the University of Newcastle, observed that simple historic cues - such as vintage typography - can enhance trust and perceived product quality, especially in developing contexts where such imagery resonates with communal memory.

These findings suggest that *historic references* not only deepen emotional engagement but also help brands stand out by rooting their messaging in what audiences already value and recognise.

6. Subtle Parodic Intertextual References

Subtle parodic intertextual references use gentle imitation of familiar adverts or cultural forms to create irony and a sense of insider understanding. *Mintiero (2023)* calls this meta-parody, which helps make brands seem more trustworthy. Studies show that subtle parody makes people more likely to engage with and share adverts, without harming how they view the brand (*Vanden Bergh et al., 2011*). Compared to obvious parody, subtle parody is safer and more effective in advertising. *Sabri and Michel (2014)* found that parodies mixing strong credibility with humour can seriously damage brand loyalty. Their research highlights that even subtle parodies, if perceived as credible critiques, can have lasting negative effects on brand image.

Image 13. *U-Fresh* advert mimicking a political debate format. Source: *Crafthouse Malawi, 2023*. Available at: <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=2663337853755746> [Accessed 3 Aug. 2025].

In 2019, *U-Fresh* released an [advert mocking rival tablet soaps](#) through symbolism and subtle parody. Amid growing market competition, it featured mascots with flawed appearances - crooked teeth, bandages - contrasted with a clean, well-lit *U-Fresh* mascot. The advert mirrored a political campaign debate, reinforcing *U-Fresh's* message of superiority and reliability.

7. Narrative Intertextual Reference

The study found out that *narrative intertextuality* occurs when an advertisement incorporates elements of existing stories, plots, or character arcs from other media texts. This can involve referencing well-known customers to create meaning through familiar narrative structures. This approach ensures adverts tap into audiences' prior knowledge and emotional investment, enhancing engagement and interpretive depth. National Bank of Malawi featured Rose Chisowa in a promotional video highlighting how its financial services supported the growth of her farming business. This aligns with the “*Rags to Riches*” and “*Transformation*” narrative types, which are widely used in brand storytelling to evoke personal growth and upward mobility (Booker, 2004; Fog et al., 2010). Such narratives help humanise the brand and build emotional resonance with audiences by showcasing real-life progress through brand involvement (Escalas, 2004).

Image 14. Screenshot of Rose Chisowa from her narrative video featured on National Bank of Malawi's YouTube page (2023).

Link: <https://youtu.be/MJFZa3x9rxk?si=WfBYafTosnohp7f9>

Recent scholarship highlights the strategic use of *narrative intertextuality* in advertising to build brand storytelling that resonates on multiple levels (Ryan & Thon, 2021). This approach leverages shared cultural scripts, enabling brands to position themselves within broader social and emotional narratives. Research also shows that narrative intertextuality can increase memorability and persuasion by embedding brands within recognisable and meaningful story frameworks, especially when the references align with target audiences' cultural context (Kim & McMillan, 2022). Based on the description of Rose Chisowa's profile in a National Bank video showcasing how their financial product helped her farming business grow, the subcategory of indirect intertextuality is *Narrative References*, specifically the “*Rags to Riches*” and potentially “*Transformation*” narrative types.

8. Implicit UCG

Implicit user-generated intertextuality involves subtle audience-created content - such as memes - that brands reference indirectly and often without clear acknowledgement (Almaghouth & Saleh, 2024). These forms emerge within participatory digital cultures where users co-create meaning, influencing brand engagement through behavioural motives tied to sharing and community interaction (Almaghouth & Saleh, 2024). Jenkins, Ford, and Green's *The concept of spreadable media*, by Jenkins et al., (2013), shows how such content extends brand narratives beyond formal marketing channels, enabling dynamic user participation. However, the unpredictable nature of user-generated content poses challenges for brand control and consistent messaging (Naeem & Okafor, 2019).

Image 15. TNM advert employing *Implicit UGC Intertextual References* following increase of the TNM Super League Prize Money. Source: TNM Malawi Facebook Page. Link: <https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=814357650737609&set=pb.100064901431436.-2207520000&type=3> (Accessed: 27 July, 2025).

In 2023, amid public criticism over the “meagre TNM Super League prize money,” TNM repurposed select negative comments to produce an advert announcing an increase. Captioned “*Munayankhula*” (“*You had your say, we listened,*”) the advert positioned the brand as responsive to public sentiment. The subtlety lay in the anonymisation of usernames, which hinted at critique without directly exposing individuals.

9. Temporal Intertextual References

Temporal intertextuality relies on timing, seasons, or current events to shape how messages are received. Briggs and Bauman (1992) argue that references to past genres or events carry social power, giving adverts authority or emotional weight. Androutsopoulos (2014) adds that media often reuses past discourse to enhance meaning in new contexts.

Image 16. Advert commemorating Kamuzu Day. Source: NBS Bank Facebook Page, 2025. Available at:

<https://www.facebook.com/nbs.malawi/posts/pfbid02du2qxGGWD96HqfnLR28fivbeRb9yOGSGU7YCqzK2dgrx48LnHfM3kyDCJSt64WiUl> [Accessed 14 May, 2025].

In advertising, this includes drawing on national holidays, past campaigns, or seasonal behaviours to create relevance. In Malawi, such references are used during public holidays such as Independence Day, Kamuzu Day or planting seasons, anchoring brand messages in familiar *cultural timelines*.

10. Comparative Intertextuality

In this study, comparative intertextuality refers to adverts that hint at rival brands without naming them. This is common in settings where open comparisons may cause conflict or raise legal issues (Beard, 2014). In Malawi, advertisers often take this indirect approach due to both regulatory caution and a cultural preference for subtlety (De Mooij, 2019).

In the telecoms sector, only Airtel is a direct competitor to TNM. Other players are too small to matter in strategic terms. TNM's line, "The network that actually works," is a clear example. Though Airtel is not named, the comparison is obvious. Such adverts rely on the audience picking up the reference. In cultures like Malawi's, this kind of indirect messaging is often seen as more credible and less aggressive by the audience (Cheng & Ho, 2015).

Image 17. TNM advert making a comparative reference to other networks. Source: Telekom Networks Malawi, 2023. Available at: <https://www.facebook.com/Telekomnetworksmalawi/posts/pfbid0zTAt7orVivx8VHp3Z3WwWtbAcwNpyLq9fa4FiDyr8gxaiLVLb4EaNBZa2W6aNeQxl> [Accessed 3 Aug. 2025].

Typically, comparative adverts are explicit, making this finding noteworthy and worthy of future research. Nine per cent (9%) of the adverts analysed fell into this category.

C. Non-Referential Adverts

The study established that non-referential adverts are used for *Brand Communication*, *Product Communication* and *Crisis Communication* when clarity and trust are essential, such as during crises, corporate announcements, or service updates. These adverts avoid cultural or symbolic references to prevent confusion, focusing instead on direct, functional messaging. This approach is common in sectors like retail, parastatals and NGOs, where straightforward communication builds credibility and ensures broad understanding (Coombs, 2015; De Mooij, 2019; Lagerwerf & Meijers, 2008).

Image 18. Non-Referential Adverts by Lilongwe Water Board (L) and National Bank of Malawi (R). Source: Facebook

iii. Grounded Intertextuality Categorisation Framework

Further to the discussion above, **Table 4** presents the *Grounded Intertextuality Categorisation Framework*, developed through the grounded theory study. It uses an “If–Then” model to classify how adverts engage with other texts, audiences, and cultural contexts. This framework works as a practical tool for analysing adverts and uncovering the strategic and tactical drivers behind Malawian digital advertising.

Table 4: *Grounded Intertextuality Categorisation Framework*

IF the advert...	THEN it uses...	IF NOT...	THEN it likely uses...
Explicitly references or mimics another advert, message, or media	Direct Intertextuality	Does not reference other messages or adverts	Non-Referential Advertising
Calls out a competitor or introduces a controversial/contentious issue	<i>Confrontational</i>	Avoids naming, provoking, or introducing controversy	Not Confrontational
Refers to contentious issues or public discussions without direct involvement	<i>Bystander</i>	Lacks commentary as a neutral third party	Not Bystander
Imitates or mocks another advert or social issue in a humorous way	<i>Parodic</i>	Has an original or serious tone	Not Parodic
Responds to brand attacks from a competitor	<i>Retaliatory</i>	Initiates new messaging without response	Not Retaliatory
References or builds on another campaign/brand in a supportive way	<i>Collaborative</i>	Does not connect or align with others	Not Collaborative
Encourages or uses user-generated content (e.g. quotes, videos, reactions)	<i>User Generated Content (UGC)</i>	Created solely by brand without audience input	Not UGC
Links to another medium (e.g. QR code, website, app, video)	<i>Cross-Media</i>	Message is self-contained	Not Cross-Media
Gains new meaning through reinterpretation or sharing by local audiences	<i>eWOM Spillover</i>	Was not audience-driven or locally recontextualised	Not eWOM Spillover
Draws on shared emotion such as hope, pride, or frustration	<i>Emotional</i>	Does not appeal to public/shared emotion	Not Emotional Reference
Implies a reference without naming it directly	Indirect Intertextuality	Is explicit or contains no reference	Not Indirect Intertextuality
Leaves meaning unclear until a later reveal (e.g. twist)	<i>Suspended/Delayed</i>	Message is direct and immediate	Not Delayed Reference

Uses idioms, traditions, or social norms	<i>Cultural</i>	Uses generic or international language	Not Cultural Reference
Refers to past events or shared history	<i>Historic</i>	Makes no reference to the past	Not Historic
Relies on timing, seasons, or current events	<i>Temporal</i>	Is not tied to any moment or event	Not Temporal
Invites audience to engage via puzzles, quizzes, or games	<i>Gamified</i>	Contains no puzzles, quizzes, or games	Not Gamification
Softly mocks or replays familiar ideas without overt satire	<i>Subtle Parodic</i>	Is original or non-mimetic	Not Subtle Parodic
Tells a story or uses a plot	<i>Narrative</i>	Offers static or factual presentation	Not Narrative-Based
Uses indirect comparison (e.g. "faster than others")	<i>Comparative</i>	Does not compare or claim superiority	Not Comparative
Refers to typical user behaviour without quoting them	<i>Implicit UGC</i>	Does not reflect user behaviours or voices	Not Implicit UGC
Focuses only on the brand or product without outside references	Non-Referential	Makes no connection to other texts, users, or cultural signs	Purely Informational
Direct messaging to control damage or clarify facts	Crisis Communication	Does not control damage or clarify facts	Not Crisis Communication
Focuses on identity, values, and brand promise	Brand Communication	Avoids focusing on identity, values, and brand promise	Not Brand Communication
Outlines features and benefits clearly	Service Product Communication	Avoids features and benefits	Not Service/Product Communication

Following grounded theory methods, a validating literature review was undertaken to test the strength of the emerging categorisation. It served two purposes: to assess whether the identified intertextual references align with established marketing theory, and to understand how such references are treated in practice. The review confirmed that these patterns are not isolated; they reflect broader strategic and theoretical marketing frameworks. The resulting *Grounded Intertextuality Categorisation* captures how intertextuality functions in Malawian advertising and how it fits within academic understanding. This alignment strengthens the framework's conceptual and practical value.

Using intertextual references with strategic intent is a marker of informed marketing. These references do not replace key strategies like positioning, differentiation, or engagement but support them. For example, *confrontational references* help competitive positioning through tactics such as *brand wars* and *combative advertising* (Ries & Trout, 1981; Beard, 2011). *Parodic* references improve *engagement, recall and emotional connection* (Weinberger & Gulas, 1992). Cultural and historical references enhance relevance by linking the brand to identity, values, and memory (Holt, 2004; Stern, 1992). Collaborative references, including co-branding and user-generated content, strengthen engagement and trust through community

involvement and social proof (*Morgan & Hunt, 1994; Cialdini, 2001*). Gamified elements improve interaction and motivation (*Huotari & Hamari, 2017*). Subtle cues such as metaphor, narrative, and allusion help drive differentiation and long-term brand positioning (*Porter, 1980; Ries & Trout, 1981*). Strategic intertextuality sharpens storytelling, improves message delivery, and reinforces broader marketing goals. See *Table 4* below for details.

You will note that figures of speech (a characteristic of subtle communication) is listed on a *direct reference*. This is because intertextuality involves multiple layers of meaning, where subtle references accumulate to create a more *overt* or *unmistakable message* (*Kristeva, 1980; Genette, 1997*).

Table 5: Evidence of Intertextuality and Marketing Strategy Linkages

Intertextuality Category	Marketing Strategy	Communicative Elements
Direct References		
Confrontational References	Brand Wars (<i>Ries & Trout, 1981</i>), Combative Advertising (<i>Beard, 2011</i>) Hijacked Advertising (<i>Thota and Villarreal, 2020</i>)	<i>Blended figures of speech, mimicry, parody</i>
By-Stander References	Positioning (<i>Ries & Trout, 1981</i>) Ambush marketing (<i>Burton & Chadwick, 2017; Dickson & Phelps, 2014; Meenaghan, 1998</i>)	<i>Implicit communicative devices blended with trending narratives</i>
Parodic References	Humorous Advertising (<i>Weinberger & Gulas, 1992</i>)	<i>Humorous or parodic strategies</i>
Retaliatory References	Counterattack Strategies (<i>Kotler & Keller, 2011</i>), Competitive Response (<i>Day & Reibstein, 1997</i>)	<i>Argumentative tactics</i>
Collaborative References	Co-Branding (<i>Blackett & Boad, 1999</i>), Collaborative Marketing (<i>Morgan & Hunt, 1994</i>)	<i>Relationship-building devices</i>
UGC/Participatory References	User-Generated Content (<i>Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010</i>) Community Marketing (<i>Muniz & O'Guinn, 2001</i>) Social Proof in Marketing (<i>Cialdini, 2001</i>) Crowdsourced Advertising (<i>Howe, 2006</i>)	<i>Digital community references</i>
Cross-Media References	Cross-Promotions (<i>Andrews & Kim, 2007</i>), Transmedia Storytelling (<i>Jenkins, 2006</i>)	<i>Message cohesion tactics</i>
Emotional Reference	Brand Positioning (<i>Ries and Trout, 1981</i>)	<i>Meaning-building strategies</i>
Indirect (Subtle) References		
Suspended/ Delayed	Brand Positioning (<i>Ries and Trout,</i>	<i>Indirect meaning devices</i>

References	2001) Differentiation , (Porter, 1980)	
Cultural References	Cultural Branding (Holt, 2004) Glocalization (Robertson, 1995) Multicultural Marketing (Cui, 2001)	<i>Cultural referencing tools</i>
Historical References	Heritage Marketing (Urde et al., 2007) Nostalgia in Advertising (Stern, 1992) Historical Positioning (Hakala et al., 2011)	<i>Historical parallels</i>
Subtle Parodic References	Implicit Marketing (Shapiro, 1999) Suggestive Advertising (Hawkins et al., 2004) Innuendo in Marketing (Gass & Seiter, 2011)	<i>Subtle rhetorical techniques</i>
Narrative References	Storytelling in Marketing (Fog et al., 2005), Brand Narratives (Escalas, 2004)	<i>Narrative devices</i>
Cross-Media References	Integrated Marketing Communications (Schultz et al., 1993) Multichannel Marketing (Neslin et al., 2006) Omnichannel Strategy (Rigby, 2011) Cross-Promotions (Andrews & Kim, 2007) Transmedia Storytelling (Jenkins, 2006)	<i>Multimedia adaptation strategies</i>
UGC/Participatory References (Subtle)	User-Generated Content (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010) Community Marketing (Muniz & O'Guinn, 2001) Social Proof in Marketing (Cialdini, 2001) Influencer Marketing (Freberg et al., 2011) Crowdsourced Advertising (Howe, 2006) Subvertising (Leal-Rico et al., 2023)	<i>Online community expressions</i>
Gamified	Gamification (Huotari & Hamari, 2017), (Xi & Hamari, 2020), (Hofacker, et al., 2016).	<i>Engagement drivers</i>
Temporal References	Real-Time Marketing (Wang, 2012) Event-Driven Marketing (Ghosh & Swaminathan, 2001) Seasonal Advertising (Ang, 2001) Time-Sensitive Promotions (Grewal et al., 1996) Contextual Advertising (Murray & Haubl, 2007)	<i>Contextual and referential devices</i>

eWOM Reference	Spillover	Electronic word-of-mouth (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004; Cheung & Thadani, 2012; Ismagilova, Slade, Rana, & Dwivedi, 2017)	<i>Engagement and meaning-making processes</i>
Comparative References		Comparative Advertising (Pechmann & Stewart, 1990) Benchmarking in Marketing (Camp, 1989)	<i>Persuasive contrasts</i>
Non-Referential Advertising			
General Branding		Corporate Branding (Balmer, 2001) Brand Awareness (Keller, 1993)	<i>Core messaging qualities</i>
Service Highlights		Service Marketing (Lovelock, 1983) Service Quality (Parasuraman et al., 1985) Customer Service Excellence (Zeithaml et al., 1990)	<i>Strategic communication elements</i>
Crisis Communication		Crisis Response Strategies (Coombs, 2007) Situational Crisis Communication Theory (SCCT) (Coombs & Holladay, 2002) Reputation Management in Crises (Fearn-Banks, 2007)	<i>Trust-building strategies</i>

Source: Mnela, M. (2025). Decoding References in Malawian Digital Advertising (unpublished)

iv. Distribution of Intertextuality Type

Table 6 below shows the distribution of intertextual reference types in a sample of 500 digital adverts. The typology distinguishes three main categories: *Direct*, *Indirect*, and *Non-Referential adverts*. Each category includes subtypes - such as emotional, cultural, temporal, and crisis communication - that represent common communicative strategies. Indirect intertextuality is most prevalent, appearing in 56% ($n = 280$) of adverts, followed by *Non-Referential adverts* at 31.8% ($n = 159$), and *Direct references* at 12.2% ($n = 61$). This pattern indicates a clear preference for subtle, indirect references - like cultural cues and temporal links - over explicit intertextuality, showing that advertisers tend to use indirect strategies to engage audiences.

Table 6: Adverts classified by their use of intertextual references

Reference Type	Subcategory	Adverts (n)	%
Direct	<i>Emotional</i>	12	2.4%
	<i>Confrontational</i>	8	1.6%
	<i>Parodic</i>	10	1.6%
	<i>Retaliatory</i>	2	1.6%

	<i>Bystander</i>	8	1.6%
	<i>Collaborative</i>	6	1.2%
	<i>User-Generated Content</i>	10	1.2%
	<i>Cross-Media</i>	5	1.0%
	Total Direct	61	12.2%
Indirect	<i>Cultural</i>	95	19.0%
	<i>Temporal</i>	75	15.0%
	<i>Narrative</i>	31	6.2%
	<i>Comparative</i>	25	5.0%
	<i>Subtle Parodic</i>	17	3.4%
	<i>Historic</i>	16	3.2%
	<i>Implicit UGC</i>	6	1.2%
	<i>Delayed Referencing</i>	6	1.2%
	<i>eWOM Spillover</i>	5	1.0%
	<i>Gamified</i>	4	0.8%
	Total Indirect	280	56.0%
Non-Referential	<i>Service Promotion</i>	117	23.4%
	<i>Brand Communication</i>	29	5.8%
	<i>Crisis Communication</i>	13	2.6%
	Total (No References)	159	31.8%
	Grand Total	500	100%

Further to the above, below is **Table 7** showing a breakdown of adverts based on sector.

Table 6: *Breakdown of Advert Based on Subcategory Distribution*

Sector	Direct Reference	Indirect Reference	Non Referential	Total
Banking	16	24	10	50
Telecommunications	15	24	11	50
FMCG	12	31	7	50
Retail	4	16	30	50
Healthcare	3	34	13	50
Education	3	35	12	50
Insurance	4	40	6	50
Hospitality	5	28	17	50
Parastatals	1	23	26	50
NGOs/Nonprofits	0	23	27	50
Total	63	278	159	500

Table 7 confirms that *indirect intertextuality* is the dominant strategy, appearing in 56.0% of adverts (280 out of 500). It is present across all sectors, highlighting its broad applicability and effectiveness.

- FMCG uses *indirect references* in 31 adverts, which is 62% of its sector total.
- Telecommunications employs *indirect references* in 24 adverts (48%).
- Banking shows indirect referencing in 24 adverts (48%).

These figures indicate a clear preference for subtle, audience-friendly messaging that avoids overt claims.

- Healthcare relies on indirect strategies in 34 adverts (68%).
- Education features indirect references in 35 adverts (70%).
- Insurance has the highest indirect use with 40 adverts (80%).

These sectors often operate in regulated or sensitive environments, making indirect cues more suitable than direct messages.

- Retail shows a stronger presence of non-referential adverts with 30 out of 50 (60%).
- Parastatals have 26 non-referential adverts (52%).
- Hospitality features 17 non-referential adverts (34%).

Such adverts typically emphasise clarity, neutrality, or an institutional tone, steering clear of complex or symbolic messaging.

- NGOs and nonprofits avoid direct referencing altogether (0 adverts). Their intertextual content is exclusively indirect, with 23 adverts (46%), or non-referential (27 adverts, 54%), likely to support advocacy and storytelling without appearing overly commercial.

4. Discussion

This study set out to fill a critical gap in advertising research by developing a grounded typology of intertextual references in Malawian digital advertising. Most existing models are Western-centric and tend to focus on style and form (e.g. *Hutcheon & O'Flynn, 2024*). In contrast, this study used a *constructivist grounded theory approach* to build a practical framework that shows how intertextuality serves marketing goals in a distinct sub-Saharan African market. The resulting typology - comprising *Direct, Indirect, and Non-Referential categories with 21 subtypes* - offers both classification and insight into the strategic choices behind their use.

4.1 The Role of Intertextuality and Communicative Elements

The findings show that intertextuality in Malawian advertising is not just about referencing other texts. It is a deliberate strategy to work within shared meaning systems.

Direct Intertextuality (12.2%)

Though less common, *direct references* are used for brand positioning and open competition. This includes visual mimicry, explicit wordplay, direct appeals, and brand confrontations. Some brands also use co-branding, mutual tagging, and shared aesthetics to build alliances. Cross-media references (e.g. *QR codes, news formats*) extend reach and credibility. Direct use of user-generated content (UGC) can boost authenticity if done right (*Marwick & Lewis, 2023*). Emotional appeals often rely on nostalgic visuals or music, such as in the TNM's Tiago no frills phone advert. This approach is clear-cut and meant to be instantly recognisable.

Indirect Intertextuality (56.0%)

This is the most common form and reflects a preference for subtlety and cultural familiarity. It includes symbolic imagery, staged reveals, idioms, and implied comparisons. Teaser formats like National Bank's mystery briefcase campaign build suspense (*Yang & Smith, 2009*). Reposted content and local memes show how brands adapt narratives through digital word-of-mouth (*Lobato, 2019*). Gamified references like branded quizzes or puzzles encourage interaction (*Hamari & Keronen, 2021*). Cultural references - local slang, customs, and symbols - anchor campaigns in shared experience (*De Mooij, 2019*). Historical references draw on national milestones or figures to build trust. Subtle parody uses ironic tones or soft mimicry without confrontation (*Mintiero, 2023*). Narrative strategies tap into familiar story arcs (*Booker, 2004*), while some brands indirectly acknowledge public sentiment or UGC without naming it. This reliance on inference and shared context aligns with high-context communication norms.

Non-Referential Adverts (31.8%)

Many adverts avoid external references altogether. Instead, they use factual content, product features, and clear messaging, especially in regulated sectors or during crises. The focus is on clarity, credibility, and control. This shows that non-intertextuality can be a deliberate strategy, particularly where misinterpretation could undermine trust.

4.2 Theoretical Contributions

This study offers several contributions to intertextuality research:

4.2.1 Form and Function

Most models describe what types of references appear. This study goes further by showing how these are used to meet marketing goals. It connects creative choices to strategic intent.

4.2.2 Local Context

Existing theories (*e.g. Genette, 1997; Kristeva, 1980*) rarely fit digital contexts in emerging markets. This study provides a grounded alternative, shaped by Malawi's cultural and media landscape. The popularity of indirect and non-referential strategies shows that Western assumptions do not always apply.

4.2.3 Scope of Intertextuality

Identifying *Non-Referential adverts* as a strategic category is a novel insight. It shows that avoiding references can be just as meaningful, especially when clarity and control are priorities.

4.2.4 Empirical Rigour

The typology was validated through a Delphi process with both academics and practitioners, strengthening its relevance for theory and practice.

4.3 Practical Implications and Future Research

This typology has practical use across sectors:

4.3.1 Marketers

Marketers can use it to design campaigns that reflect local culture and audience preferences. It helps in deciding when to be direct, subtle, or entirely self-referential - choices that affect engagement and trust.

4.3.2 Regulators and Policy Makers

Regulators and policymakers can use the framework to understand how references operate in local advertising, guiding rules on fair competition, content ownership, and responsible messaging.

4.3.3 Researchers

Researchers can build on this work through comparative studies in similar markets or audience-focused research on how intertextual messages are received. Longitudinal studies can also track changes over time in response to new technology or shifts in consumer culture.

5. Significance/Contributions of the Study

This is the first empirical study to examine intertextuality in Malawian digital advertising through grounded theory, using a robust five-year dataset. Previous African research on intertextuality has mostly focused on print media or discourse analysis, with limited attention to digital practices. For example, *Van Niekerk (2005)* showed how South African print adverts use shared cultural references to reflect dominant worldviews. *Conradie (2012)* identified both explicit and implicit references in adverts that shape product meanings. *Enesiti (2010)* demonstrated how intertextuality in Botswana's print adverts blends language, culture, and social messages to navigate sectoral competition and restrictions.

This study shifts the focus to digital advertising, proposing a three-part typology - *Direct, Indirect, and Non-Referential adverts* - that captures how brands strategically use or avoid use of intertextuality in a culturally grounded way. It fills a clear gap in the literature, provides advertisers with a practical framework, and establishes a foundation for comparative research across sub-Saharan Africa.

6. Limitations of the Study

This study set out to understand how intertextuality appears in Malawian digital advertising and to build a clear typology based on real examples. Analysing 500 adverts across ten sectors using grounded theory, we created a three-part framework: *Direct References, Indirect References, and Non-Referential Advertising*. These categories, with their subtypes, offer a practical and adaptable way to see how meaning is made and shared in Malawi's digital adverts.

Our findings reveal a strong preference for *indirect intertextuality*. Malawian advertisers rely on subtle cultural hints, current digital trends, and shared social knowledge to craft messages that resonate deeply. Direct attacks - whether *confrontational* or *retaliatory* - are notably rare, showing that brands avoid overt conflict and favour more subtle communication.

While *direct references* do appear, mainly in competitive sectors, many adverts avoid intertextuality altogether, focusing instead on clear and straightforward information. This mix shows a careful balance between cultural connection and clear communication suited to the local market.

This typology offers both theoretical and practical value. For researchers, it provides an African-centred alternative to mostly Western models, enriching how we understand advertising worldwide. For practitioners, it gives a solid tool to create effective campaigns that respect cultural complexity and layer meaning thoughtfully to engage audiences online. As digital advertising grows, this work opens the door for further research on how this typology applies across cultures and how different audiences interpret intertextual references in a global yet local media world.

7. Key Contributions

1. Practice-Oriented Typology

The study proposes a simplified categorisation of intertextual references, grounded in observed advertising practice. While rooted in real-world use, the typology also engages with and challenges existing theory, offering locally relevant examples that refine how intertextuality is understood in Malawian advertising.

2. Contextual Challenge to Global Models

Findings question the assumption that global advertising theories apply uniformly. While comparative intertextuality is often defined as overt, adverts in this study primarily used subtle, indirect forms. This may reflect cultural sensitivities or a general tendency toward risk aversion in the local industry.

3. Regulatory Framework

The typology offers a tool for identifying ethical breaches and guiding both internal and external regulation of advert content. It also enables detection of *reference fatigue or reference* - where excessive reuse of certain references in adverts weakens their impact (Tayeb et al., 2025).

4. Strong Empirical Base

The study draws on a diverse sample of 500 digital adverts across sectors and platforms, ensuring findings are grounded in actual practice rather than assumption. However, existing theory is used to validate and contextualise the grounded theory after its development, in line with the constant comparative method and theoretical integration principles (Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Charmaz, 2014; Corbin & Strauss, 2008).

8. Areas for Further Research

i. Development of Local Evaluation Models

Future work should focus on building a context-specific framework to help advertisers create intertextual content that is culturally relevant, strategic, ethical, and measurable in impact.

ii. Audience Reception Analysis

Research is needed to understand how different demographic groups interpret intertextual references, especially across language, age, and rural - urban divides.

iv Ethical and Legal Boundaries

There is a need to examine the ethical and legal implications of referencing public figures, competitors, and cultural symbols in digital adverts, particularly in unregulated environments.

v. Longitudinal Trends in Intertextuality

Tracking changes in intertextual practice over time could reveal how advertising strategies shift in response to evolving cultural, political, and technological contexts.

9. Conclusion

This study presents the first grounded typology of intertextuality in Malawian digital advertising, developed from a systematic analysis of 500 adverts across ten sectors. The framework offers a critical lens for understanding both the construction of meaning and the operationalisation of strategic communication in Malawi's evolving digital advertising landscape.

Findings show a strong preference for *indirect intertextuality*, highlighting advertisers' skill in using subtle cultural cues, contemporary trends, and shared social knowledge to create persuasive, resonant messages and avoid reference fatigue. *Direct references* appear mainly in competitive contexts, while many campaigns deliberately avoid *intertextuality*, favouring clarity and straightforward messaging through *non-referential adverts*. This balance reflects a strategic blend of cultural resonance and communication efficiency - an important local insight.

The typology makes both theoretical and practical contributions. Theoretically, it provides a context-specific alternative to dominant Western models, enriching the study of advertising in African markets and offering a template for region-focused communication research. Practically, it gives advertisers and strategists a robust, empirically derived tool for developing culturally informed, effective, and ethically grounded campaigns in the Malawian context. As digital advertising continues to evolve, this research establishes a foundation for future work, including audience reception studies, demographic comparisons within Malawi, and cross-cultural analyses of the typology's global applicability.

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Appendix 2: Proportion of Agreement (P_i) Across Advert Categories

Advert - ID	Coders Direct	Coders Indirect	Coders Non-Referential	P_i
1	18 ▾	1 ▾	1 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
2	19 ▾	1 ▾	0 ▾	0.9 ▾
3	20 ▾	0 ▾	0 ▾	1 ▾
4	18 ▾	1 ▾	1 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
5	20 ▾	0 ▾	0 ▾	1 ▾
6	18 ▾	2 ▾	0 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾
7	18 ▾	1 ▾	1 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
8	20 ▾	0 ▾	0 ▾	1 ▾
9	18 ▾	1 ▾	1 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
10	18 ▾	1 ▾	1 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
11	20 ▾	0 ▾	0 ▾	1 ▾
12	20 ▾	0 ▾	0 ▾	1 ▾

Advert ID	Coders Direct	Coders Indirect	Coders NonReferential	P_i
13	1 ▾	17 ▾	2 ▾	0.7210526316 ▾
14	4 ▾	15 ▾	1 ▾	0.5842105263 ▾
15	0 ▾	19 ▾	1 ▾	0.9 ▾
16	1 ▾	18 ▾	1 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
17	3 ▾	17 ▾	0 ▾	0.7315789474 ▾
18	3 ▾	17 ▾	0 ▾	0.7315789474 ▾
19	2 ▾	15 ▾	3 ▾	0.5736842105 ▾
20	2 ▾	16 ▾	2 ▾	0.6421052632 ▾

21	2 ▾	17 ▾	1 ▾	0.7210526316 ▾
22	1 ▾	18 ▾	1 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
23	0 ▾	20 ▾	0 ▾	1 ▾
24	3 ▾	16 ▾	1 ▾	0.6473684211 ▾
25	1 ▾	15 ▾	4 ▾	0.5842105263 ▾
26	2 ▾	17 ▾	1 ▾	0.7210526316 ▾
27	1 ▾	18 ▾	0 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
28	0 ▾	20 ▾	0 ▾	1 ▾
29	2 ▾	17 ▾	2 ▾	0.7263157895 ▾
30	1 ▾	16 ▾	3 ▾	0.6473684211 ▾
31	2 ▾	17 ▾	1 ▾	0.7210526316 ▾
32	0 ▾	18 ▾	2 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾
33	0 ▾	20 ▾	0 ▾	1 ▾
34	2 ▾	16 ▾	2 ▾	0.6421052632 ▾
35	2 ▾	15 ▾	3 ▾	0.5736842105 ▾
36	3 ▾	17 ▾	0 ▾	0.7315789474 ▾
37	1 ▾	18 ▾	1 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
38	0 ▾	20 ▾	0 ▾	1 ▾
39	0 ▾	17 ▾	3 ▾	0.7315789474 ▾
40	2 ▾	16 ▾	2 ▾	0.6421052632 ▾
41	0 ▾	18 ▾	2 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾
42	1 ▾	18 ▾	1 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
43	1 ▾	16 ▾	3 ▾	0.6473684211 ▾
44	1 ▾	18 ▾	1 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾

Advert_ID	Coders Direct	Coders Indirect	Coders NonReferential	P_i
45	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
46	1 ▾	0 ▾	19 ▾	0.9 ▾
47	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
48	1 ▾	1 ▾	18 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
49	2 ▾	1 ▾	17 ▾	0.7210526316 ▾
50	2 ▾	2 ▾	16 ▾	0.6421052632 ▾
51	2 ▾	0 ▾	18 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾
52	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
53	0 ▾	1 ▾	19 ▾	0.9 ▾
54	2 ▾	2 ▾	16 ▾	0.6421052632 ▾
55	3 ▾	2 ▾	15 ▾	0.5736842105 ▾
56	2 ▾	2 ▾	16 ▾	0.6421052632 ▾
57	1 ▾	1 ▾	18 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
58	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
59	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
60	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
61	2 ▾	0 ▾	18 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾
62	0 ▾	4 ▾	16 ▾	0.6631578947 ▾
63	4 ▾	2 ▾	14 ▾	0.5157894737 ▾
64	2 ▾	3 ▾	16 ▾	0.6526315789 ▾
65	4 ▾	0 ▾	16 ▾	0.6631578947 ▾
66	2 ▾	0 ▾	18 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾
67	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
68	0 ▾	2 ▾	18 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾

69	0 ▾	4 ▾	16 ▾	0.6631578947 ▾
70	1 ▾	3 ▾	17 ▾	0.7315789474 ▾
71	0 ▾	2 ▾	18 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾
72	0 ▾	1 ▾	19 ▾	0.9 ▾
73	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
74	1 ▾	1 ▾	18 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
75	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
76	1 ▾	2 ▾	17 ▾	0.7210526316 ▾
77	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
78	2 ▾	0 ▾	18 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾
79	0 ▾	1 ▾	19 ▾	0.9 ▾
80	0 ▾	2 ▾	18 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾
81	1 ▾	2 ▾	17 ▾	0.7210526316 ▾
82	0 ▾	4 ▾	16 ▾	0.6631578947 ▾
83	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
84	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
85	1 ▾	1 ▾	18 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
86	2 ▾	0 ▾	18 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾
87	1 ▾	1 ▾	18 ▾	0.8052631579 ▾
88	1 ▾	0 ▾	19 ▾	0.9 ▾
89	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
90	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
91	2 ▾	2 ▾	16 ▾	0.6421052632 ▾
92	4 ▾	2 ▾	14 ▾	0.5157894737 ▾
93	1 ▾	2 ▾	17 ▾	0.7210526316 ▾

94	2 ▾	3 ▾	15 ▾	0.5736842105 ▾
95	0 ▾	0 ▾	20 ▾	1 ▾
96	2 ▾	4 ▾	14 ▾	0.5157894737 ▾
97	2 ▾	2 ▾	16 ▾	0.6421052632 ▾
98	1 ▾	2 ▾	17 ▾	0.7210526316 ▾
99	0 ▾	3 ▾	17 ▾	0.7315789474 ▾
100	0 ▾	2 ▾	18 ▾	0.8105263158 ▾